

AN UNTRUSTWORTHY EDITION

(a review of F. Zufferey, *La chanson de saint Alexis, essai d'édition critique de la version primitive*, Paris, SATF, 2020, 654 p.)

A Norman adventurer amazed at the sight of the city of Alsis, goes back home and tells his friend the *trouvère* about his own experience. The *trouvère* finds inspiration to compose a poem, which a German-speaking admirer decides to translate, so that even a German can understand it. Finally, a Burgundian rewriter, shocked by Alexis' mother's breast nudity, submits the text to censorship.

The plot becomes even more intriguing when one realizes that the vision of the city nestled on the cliffs (it can easily be found on the web) dates back at least to the next century. That the German-speaking admirer is much more reasonably a prelate well-versed in Church affairs during the First Crusade. That the Burgundian so imbued with puritan spirit speaks a coarse Norman dialect on the border with Picardy.

Obviously, all of this does not exist in the manuscripts, but is the work of an editor (whom I will call FZ) who does not lack imagination, but has only imperfect knowledge in linguistics and philology, which he often tries to remedy by means of not-so-focused Google searches. He shares with a part of the Helvetic tradition a taste for Zumthor's *mouvance* and the myth of oral poetry. He is no stranger to Dragonetti's pseudo-etymological devices. He has probably spent a lot of time in university classrooms studying ancient pluperfects.

Two conflicting vectors can be recognized in his edition. On the one hand, an antiquated, and undoubtedly rigid, conception of grammar *d'oïl*, for which he reveals important bibliographical gaps. On the other hand, a labored attempt to make himself competent within the framework of Italian-brand neolachmannism: I counted no less than 64 occurrences of the term *diffraction*, and 19 of the term *facteur dynamique*.

FZ starts from the assumption of a Life of Alexis already complete in all its parts, but coexisting with a shortened version: this is a way of solving from the outset, by recourse to contamination, a number of problems, and in particular the co-presence in ms. L of two alternative versions. It is a deductive method, proceeding not by aggregation but by what he calls *déconstruction*. The history of the text moves along through three stages, and each of them needs to be justified, which is not always easy or possible.

FZ feels an unrepressible urge to individuate and localize. In deference to the alleged role played by Lanfranc of Pavia, the place of origin of the primitive text is the abbey of Bec-Hallouin: for the purpose of making room for it, FZ is willing (tacitly, as always) to self-correct, moving from the Haute –as it was in the 2007 article– to the Basse-Normandie. The identification of Sis (which he draws from a source he always leaves unnamed) creates an annoying historical problem for him: in addition to evoking an operetta adventurer, he seeks to solve it with the pretext (found on Google) of a temporary occupation of the city by the Turks; yet historians ignore, or deny, such episode.

The other major problem is, as is well known, the relative chronology with respect to the Latin Rhythm. According to FZ, the Rhythm precedes the *Vie de saint Alexis*: as Bischoff (and Rychner) already said, the place names *Alsis*, *Licca*, *Lice* are enough to show that the Latin poem is tributary to a vernacular source. The argument is correct, except that this source is not the *Vie*, but –more probably– an identified Romano-Germanic life, initialed Sy, and critically edited by the guy whom FZ always leaves unnamed. Unwillingly, problems of conscience rise to the surface: FZ makes no mention of Sy, but curiously invents the figure of a German-speaking admirer from Gorze Abbey, of whom there is no trace in the entire Alessian tradition. But «s’il fallait sauter le relais de Gorze et passer directement à l’abbaye de Hirsau, cela n’ôterait rien à la vraisemblance du scénario» (p. 166) – here is indeed an even too loquacious slip.

The next two phases in the history of the text are based on a quite feeble justification, i.e. the addition, in each, of two interpolated stanzas. The second phase is located in Cluny, Burgundy, because the two stanzas bear the traditional label of “Cluniac”. In fact, these stanzas are already present in the Byzantine Lives and tell a whole other story of monastic rules (τυπικά), fasting, synodal debates at the time of the schism with the West, and relating to the sacrament of Communion. Moreover, linguistic analysis attests that the interpolator, as mentioned above, is not a native of Burgundy at all, but is Norman. As for Alexis’ mother exposing her breasts, it all depends on a clumsy reading of biblical places, which even in today’s times would not pass the hurdle of a general culture examination.

The third phase concerns the «strophes interpolées 81 et 83», which would have been inserted in eastern Picardy, and in particular «autour de l’abbaye de Saint-Amand, en raison du rôle joué par ce scriptorium sur les plus anciens textes». Actually one of these stanzas is from the Walloon region, the other is probably Anglo-Norman.

The critical text is based on ms. A, but the pollution rate (i.e. the grafting of extraneous words in the text) is exceedingly high. A huge number of dynamic factors are preserved by the

ms. L alone, so FZ is forced to insert them one by one. But that is not enough. There are a great deal of words that do not exist in the text, but are reconstructed through an absurd use of diffraction. The most conspicuous examples are *polle* ‘maiden’ (vv. 102 and 592), inspired by *Eulalia*; *dis* < DIES, v. 143 (where *host* ‘army’ is another phantom word) and v. 210, also found in the early texts. *Des* ‘depuis longtemps’ (v. 116) is unheard of. The feminine pronoun *el* is nowhere to be found in the text, but FZ invents it in v. 437. The equally unrelated adverb *ilo* is reconstructed twice; *iluc* once. The adverb *sempres* ‘aussitôt’ is attested four times, but one of these (v. 437) is disguised as *s’emprès* ‘et après’. To the three actually existing pluperfects (*fired, sore, oure*) FZ adds four more: 77 *deuret*, 160 *pouret*, 163 *voldret*, 228 *guarderet*. Did someone speak of a ‘dangerous edition’? of philological tour de force? of unbridled imagination?

FZ is uncomfortable with Latin: he does not distinguish between *basium* and *osculum*; as an etymology for 581 *oriés* he invents an AUREĀTUS declared to be a nonexistent word since 1879 (another of his forgeries is *MĪRĪBĪLIA); he confuses *cernui* of the Latin Rhythm with 290 *doute*, whereas the reference is obviously to 357 *jetent sei*. On the other hand, he claims that ADMANUARE is an invention of Gaston Paris: he does not know that the verb is solidly attested since the 11th century.

FZ is even more uncomfortable with Greek: the neophyte care with which he explains entirely superfluous information says a lot. He translates 534 *mun<er>e* with ‘bienfaits’ instead of ‘relique’; 559 *espece* with ‘signe’ instead of ‘gemme’ or ‘trésor’ (χρήμα). The (incorrect) etymology of the name Alexis is taken from a site on Harry Potter; after all, *Alexis* for FZ is the genitive form (!) and *Alexin* is a «variant nasalisée».

He is also at odds with what the French call (unfortunately) *régionalismes*: actually, 254 *musgode* is located in Normandy, not Burgundy; *deplaint(e)* is Walloon, not Picard; 434 *avogrir* is not «uniquement» Picard, it is also Anglo-Norman.

Lack of mental flexibility and bibliographical information cause him to fall into errors of which a student would be ashamed on examination: «le subj. prés. de *sazir* = *saisir* n’est pas *sazist/saisist* (forme de l’indicatif), mais bien *sazisse/saisisse*, car le verbe appartient à la conjugaison inchoative». The agreement of the p.p. with the subject would be a «forgerie». One wonders what kind of revision the distinguished colleagues whom FZ thanks in the foreword have done.

This edition will go the way of Volusius’ *Annals*, to whose tradition it rightfully belongs. Obviously, not everything written in 650 pages is consistent with the standard of what I have just reported. I recommend –not without proceeding to the ritual checks– to take advantage of

the synoptic apparatus, which replaces Foerster's now unobtainable one. For the rest, there remains a doubt that is arduous to resolve. FZ deliberately ignores the previous editions edited by the Unnamed, including some articles that would have partly remedied his incompetence. Nonetheless, the whole documentation he ignores –or pretends to ignore– predates his edition by at least ten years ; so, whatever acceptable he says, it will never be known to what extent is of his own hand, or rather was tacitly drawn from the writings of the Unnamed. Some slips of the tongue are significant in this regard.

This edition handles with difficulty. The same materials are spread in two or three different places, and the internal references are not clear, nor are the titles and subtitles, and the division into chapters itself, and even the bibliography. But on a practical level, the most serious flaw is having collected in the appendix one of the two conclusions of the poem as well as several stanzas believed to be interpolated, for a total of seven stanzas. The inevitable consequence is that, in comparison with all previous editions, it skips the entire numbering of lines, with the result that those consulting this edition must necessarily have another one under hand if they do not want to undergo irritating and tiresome research for a considerable extent of the book.

This is an edition laden with preconceived notions, self-imposed silences, unspoken and heavy psychological conditioning. It is an edition stuffed not with scientific hypotheses, but with genuine errors, which therefore must eschew fair play and political correctness, and be stated for what they are. As for the systematic omission of indispensable references, this is something that comes perilously close to plagiarism, especially when dealing with an incalculable amount of data, research, and records. I am talking about all the information from the 4th century onward and the entire *cadre géographique* with Rabbula and the Monophysite circles of Edessa, the cult of St. Euphemia, the Acemetians, Abgar, the Calibita, the unloosed abbreviation *Capolim*, the «extravagance» (!) of the two Romes, the Greek archetype underlying the Roman Vitae, the 'Spanish' Vita, the Syriac (Ephrem) sources of the Rhythm, Thoros, the Admont Codex, the Latin-Germanic Vita BHL 292, Gerhoch of Reichersberg, the cult of Alexis in the abbey réseau of Hirsau, the role of Armenians in the First Crusade.

The Unnamed is evoked once or twice: «L'exposition et la discussion des nombreux points de désaccord» would have been «sans le bénéfique compensatoire d'une perception contrastée des problèmes posés par l'Alexis» (p. 13). FZ is right : taking it into account in the same capacity as the other predecessors, he had to quote it an exaggerated number of times ; it is much easier to keep silent and pick up what comes in handy.

FZ counts on the relative imperviousness of the discipline to make people believe that he has accomplished an «immense» work, destined to crush a «dangereuse» edition based on an «erroné» postulate. He hides his own radical foreignness to classical culture behind the screen of obsessive Manichaeism. It is an attitude that sullies first and foremost himself, but also those who are the object of his criticism, or to whom he expresses gratitude. The Unnamed, on the other hand, finds himself in a delicate situation: the choice is between playing the politics of the ostrich, or making clear something that ominously resembles a gigantic willful omission, or a crass imitation, if not a sordid violation of intellectual property.

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